

GUIDE, COMMENTS ON THE CONCEPT OF TRANSLATOR THE FUNCTION OF THEIR ETHICS

“Travel makes one modest. You see what a tiny place you occupy in the world”.

GUSTAVE FLAUBERT

*Uzbekistan State University of World Languages Faculty of English languages
Methodology of English language teaching №2 Senior teacher of the department
Ashurova Feruza Lutpullayevna (ashurovaferuza19765@gmail.com).*

*Uzbekistan University of State Economy and Diplomacy Faculty of Translation
The Direction of Guide Accompaniment and Translation Activities Student of
Presidential Scholar Rakhimova Charoskhon Odiljonovna (chrahimova1990@mail.ru).*

ANNOTATION.

In the tour service, the guide allows tourists to see the objects that help to illuminate the topic (the first task), to get the necessary information about these objects (the second task), to feel the essence of the historical event (the third task), to independently observe the objects of the tour and helps to develop analytical skills (fourth task). The last task is to develop the ability of tourists to see objects correctly. The ability to see objects correctly means aesthetic perception of architectural masses, colors, lines of different types, groups of objects, color gamut, lines and their complex at a certain angle of light. scan, acceptance is understood. Understanding the historical attractions of objects is manifested in: first, finding the historical and cultural identity of the object of the tour; second, to identify traces of different periods in the object of the tour; third, to find historical facts from monumental and museum-historical monuments. This process always requires a lot of knowledge and skills. The information of the tour and the skill of the guide in narrating them will allow the tourists to draw the necessary conclusions. About this Russian educator A.V. Bakushinsky said: "The methodological development of the material based on the tour plan, mission, purpose should develop the skills of independent feeling, acceptance and evaluation."

KEY WORDS.

Guide, translator, ethics, guides function, tour, tour guide, profession, guide-interpreters, tourism, tourists, travel, travel agent, recreation ares, verbal and nonverbal communication, tour centre, training center, guides certificate.

INTRODUCTION.

One of the tasks of the tour service is to form in the minds of tourists the theme of the tour, the lives of historical figures, events, facts and attitudes to the tour information in general, and an independent assessment.

Evaluation is about getting an idea of someone or something, defining its essence, character, role, recognizing someone's positive qualities and strengths. Guided tour evaluation is the process

by which a guide draws a final conclusion on a topic using the guide's instructions. Attitude to the tour service - this is a clear view of the tourist about the historical period, which is covered in the topic of the tour service; to feel a movement, to understand the mood of a writer or artist when he creates his work. Like the requirements for literary works, the tour has its own plot as the work of a specific author, and all the materials of the tour are subject to it.

Excursion services are a more complex process than in-person tour information or instructor interviews on tourist trips, depending on their mission and format. The thematic tour service differs from the city exhibition tour in its structure, content and complexity in terms of style. The development of the tour depends on its content. The tour was originally called a trip to search for medicinal plants, and later it was set for scientific purposes, such as collecting samples from local history museums. The search for new forms of independent learning has set general educational goals for the excursion service. Efforts to organize educational work more effectively have made the excursion service one of the cultural and educational activities.

Now the tour service is completed as an individual methodology, has a purposeful, unique function and features. It is significantly enriched in terms of content, format, presentation of information and has been described as an integral part of ideological, educational, cultural and public work.

This means that the tour service is a visual process in the study of the human environment, in which objects located in natural conditions, in enterprise buildings, laboratories, research institutes and other places are pre-selected.

DISCUSSION

Professional history

The name of the profession comes from the French word "guide", which means "guide". Thus, it can be called any nation that knows a particular area and the customs of its inhabitants and accompanies the traveler who visits that area.

Many researchers believe that Thomas Cook, a British businessman who became the "father" of organized tourism, was the first real leader. In 1841 he gathered 570 people to travel by rail and accompanied them. Thomas Cook later created a tourism community and developed a series of itineraries through European and later American cities.

Description and characteristics of the profession

Now almost all guides know who they are. These are the people who first meet the guests of the city, help them stay in the hotel, and then accompany them throughout their lives. They can accompany tourists on water, bus and hiking trips.

Typically, the guide takes guests along a specific path, and the trip is accompanied by an interesting and informative story about the history of the region, its architecture, attractions, and celebrities.

6 Common Types of Quick Reference Guides

1. Quick-start guide.
2. User manual for products with limited features.
3. Core, common, or basic tasks guides.
4. Guide to more advanced features.
5. Product updates guide.
6. Step-by-step how-tos.

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However, the profession of guide requires not only conducting excursions, but also solving a number of related problems, often organizational issues.

A good guide can make a visit to the city memorable for guests, while a bad one can ruin the whole experience. Therefore, the specialist should be able to communicate with the group, correct the route if necessary, and answer the questions of tourists in a competent and interesting way. Depending on the organization of the tour and the composition of the group, the following categories of guides are distinguished:

Tourists, who can not only talk about the attractions along the bus, but also take a qualified tour of any museum, temple or historical part of the city.

Guide-interpreters serve groups of tourists who are fluent in a particular foreign language and from abroad.

Working with groups of accompanying guides Russian tourists to travel abroad.

There are also such specialists, who leave the right to conduct a separate tour to their colleagues in the museum, and they themselves focus on the organizational and administrative support of the tour. This is a big deal because tourists are not always disciplined, responsible and sincere people. Often the guide has to resolve conflicts and misunderstandings that arise.

Directions, specialties and educational institutions according to the profile of training:

Let's focus on how to be a guide. A specialist in this field should have deep knowledge and a broad outlook, so he needs higher education. Basically, humanities education in the fields of philology, cultural studies, tourism, history, art history is appropriate. You can also earn a diploma in "Excursion and Museum Studies".

Based on this knowledge, you can build your future activities. Good humanities knowledge is provided by the following universities:

Moscow State Pedagogical University. The Faculty of Geography specializes in "Technology and organization of services of tour operators and travel agencies", which trains specialists in the field of excursions.

He teaches Tourism at the Faculty of History, Political Science and Law of the Russian State University for the Humanities.

The Russian International Tourism Academy, which has branches in a number of cities across the country, offers both higher and secondary special education in tourism. Its graduates can be group guides, excursion guides, guides.

The Faculty of Tourism and Service of Sochi State University trains specialists in tourism and hospitality (bachelors and masters). There are programs "Domestic and inbound tourism" and "Organization of tourism enterprises."

Vladivostok State University of Economics and Service teaches at the Faculty of Tourism and Ecology. Here they teach in a foreign language, as well as in world culture and art.

But for a full-time job guide, in addition to graduating from university, it is recommended to take specialized courses that teach good speech, legal nuances of organizing excursions, formation. interesting routes, features of tourist psychology.

Training centers include:

The Training and Coordination Center "Guides and Guides" (Moscow) trains specialists in all areas of tourism.

Tourcenter (Moscow) tourist training center prepares guides for 4-5 months, there is an opportunity to study on weekends.

Guide skills can be divided into several groups:

- Ability to prepare a new excursion topic;
- Ability to show objects on a tour;
- Ability to tell the story of excursion objects;
- Excursion technique skills;
- Ability to present visual aids in a "guide portfolio";

- Ability to work with tourists;
- speech culture skills;
- Ability to work with books, museums, exhibitions, archives;
- Excursion preparation skills;
- Ability to advertise tours;
- Post-excursion skills.

Ethical requirements for a person are adherence to general principles and ethical norms, striving for perfection. The formation of a person in all respects is perfect and harmonious throughout his life (in high school, college, university, in the community, in everyday life, in training courses for guides, in interaction with tourists).

The formation of a guide's personality occurs during the formation of a guide's profession. The requirement for a guide's personality is that he or she adhere to general principles and norms of conduct, and adhere to clear ideas.

Quick-Reference Guide

Dos and Don'ts

Do

- ✓ Keep it as short as possible.
- ✓ Use visuals.
- ✓ Know your audience.
- ✓ Use visuals.
- ✓ Make it stand on its own.

Don't

- ✗ Cram in too much information.
- ✗ Use impossibly tiny font sizes.
- ✗ Repeat information unnecessarily.

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The main qualities of a person include:

- Wisdom - acting wisely;
- responsibility - understanding the results of their actions;
- personal reputation - actions related to the protection of their rights;
- Individuality - the uniqueness of the personality, its uniqueness.

The guide should be able to demonstrate an active outlook on life based on the nature of his or her profession and use it in his or her daily activities.

As with any educator, there are four types of guides:

- constructiveness
- organization
- communicativeness
- Analysis

The guide should use verbal, figurative, and logical emphasis correctly. Emphasis is on distinguishing a word or group of words by raising the volume or tone. The continuous work of the guide on his speech enriches the vocabulary, allows you to select and use the right words in the story, "cleanse" the speech from unnecessary words, standard phrases, as well as create an individual style of his speech allows.

Noverbal communication tools. Verbal communication affects the audience through two streams of information: the first is a continuous verbal flow, and the second is a continuous nonverbal flow.

Guide speech includes standard words such as "so", "summary", "short" and so on phrases are inappropriate. Speech fluency is also important. The tone of the guide's speech should be louder throughout the tour.

The character of the story changes depending on the tasks assigned to it. The story can be informative or reconstructive.

Travel and recreation

Explorers in the past venturing into territory unknown by their own people invariably hired guides. Military explorers [Lewis and Clark](#) were hired by the United States Congress to explore the [Pacific Northwest](#). They in turn hired the better qualified Native American [Sacagawea](#) to help them. [Wilfred Thesiger](#) hired guides in the deserts that he ventured into, such as Kuri on his journey to the [Tibesti](#) Mountains in 1938.

Tour guide

A tour guide at the [Centre Block](#) in Canada.

Tour guides lead visitors through [tourist attractions](#) and give information about the attractions' natural and cultural significance. Often, they also act as interpreters for travelers who do not speak the local language. Automated systems like [audio tours](#) are sometimes substituted for human tour guides. [Tour operators](#) often hire guides to lead tourist groups.

Mountain guide

Mountain guides are those employed in [mountaineering](#); these are not merely to show the way but stand in the position of professional climbers with an expert knowledge of rock and snowcraft, which they impart to the amateur, at the same time assuring the safety of the climbing party. This professional class of guides arose in the middle of the 19th century when Alpine climbing became recognized as a [sport](#).

In Switzerland, the central committee of the Swiss Alpine Club issues a guides' tariff which fixes the charges for guides and porters; there are three sections, for the [Valais](#) and [Valdois](#) Alps, for the [Bernese Oberland](#), and for central and eastern Switzerland.^[1]

In [Chamonix \(France\)](#) a statue has been raised to [Jacques Balmat](#), who was the first to climb [Mont Blanc](#) in 1786.^[1] Other notable European guides are [Christian Almer](#), [Jakob](#) and [Melchior Anderegg](#), [Klemens Bachleda](#), Auguste Balmat, [Alexander Burgener](#), [Armand Charlet](#), [Michel Croz](#), [François Devouassoud](#), [Angelo Dibona](#), [Andreas Heckmair](#), the [Innerekofler](#) family, [Conrad Kain](#), [Christian Klucker](#), and [Matthias Zurbriggen](#).

Wilderness guide

Adirondack guides (carrying and rowing [guideboats](#) on the [Raquette River](#), 1888

A [wilderness](#) guide leads paid parties through back country areas that may variously include land, water bodies, and high country — but not so high and technical as to require the skills of a [mountain guide](#). Wilderness guides in the United States are historically and romantically particularly associated

with the [Adirondack Mountains](#) of [New York State](#), where they first established the application of their skills as a broadly accepted and financially compensated trade.

Wilderness guides are expected to have a command of survival skills (such as making shelters, [fire-making](#), [navigation](#), and [first aid](#)) and an understanding of the [ecology](#) and [history](#) of the location where they guide. Other common skills among guides include traditional [handicrafts](#) and cooking methods, [fishing](#), [hunting](#), [bird watching](#), and [nature conservation](#).

Wilderness tours usually take place on foot, though aids such as [skis](#) and [snowshoes](#), and conveyances such as [canoes](#), [kayaks](#), [sledges](#), [pack animals](#), and [snowmobiles](#) are utilized as appropriate.^[2]

Hunting guide

Hunting guides are employed by those seeking to hunt wildlife, especially [big game](#) animals in the wild. European hunting guides working in Africa are sometimes called [white hunters](#), although the term is most commonly used in the context of the early [20th century](#).

Safari guide

Guides are employed on [safari](#), today usually just to observe and [photograph wildlife](#), historically for [big-game hunting](#). Safari guides are either self-employed or work for or through a guide service. There are no set qualifications or universal licensing procedures; customs and requirements vary by location. In lieu, many guides choose to belong to a professional association.^[3] These are typically linked to specific countries and are governed by their laws and policies. Associations such as *The Field Guides Association of Southern Africa (FGASA)*^[4] and *Uganda Safari Guides Association (USAGA)*^[5] play an important role in training and educating safari guides to improve their knowledge and group safety. Many famed safari guides are found on the [list of famous big-game hunters](#).

Fishing guide

Fishing guides have a long history. Their work spans from aiding [fly fishing](#) in small brooks or lakes to deep saltwater [big game fishing](#). Some areas where fishing guides are popular include the [Norwegian coast](#), [Swedish archipelago](#), the [Florida coast](#), and various parts of [Canada](#). The vernacular terms "fishing charter" or "charter boat" imply the services of a guide, whether the vessel's captain, a qualified hand, or experienced sportsman.

CONCLUSION

Knowledge of psychology and pedagogy will help the guide to organize the tour service properly. Properly organized interactions between guides and tourists are the basis of pedagogical processes such as excursions. The communicative component is a key part of a guide's professional skills. The effectiveness of the tour service depends not only on the knowledge of the guide on the topic, the method of its delivery to the audience, but also on the interaction with the tourists, other professionals, the driver.

Communication with the audience is also important, such as vigilance and dialogue. Excursion managers pay close attention to the role of the guide in the tour service and analyze its successes as well as its shortcomings. In order to increase the activity of tourists during the tour, the guide will have to use different options. If he covers the story more broadly, he becomes a speaker, which weakens the role of the guide in making those who see and hear feel. When a guide emphasizes information, the process is effective only if the guide focuses clearly and encourages him or her to think, compare, evaluate, and draw conclusions.

In practice, tour services can be viewed from different perspectives:

- as an independent form of education and upbringing;
 - as a form of working with a mass audience;
 - as a form of organization of cultural recreation, educational work;
 - as an episodic event, part of a thematic cycle, a step in the process of learning;
 - as a form of dissemination of scientific knowledge, as an ideological education;
 - as a type of educational direction (patriotism, diligence, aesthetic) as well as as part of the process of forming a comprehensively perfect personality;
 - absolute form and organization of cultural and educational work
- as an integral part of tourism.

The main part is based on the presentation and narration of specific excursion objects. The main part consists of several themes, summarized in one general theme and covered in objects. Topics usually range from 5 to 12. When preparing an excursion service, it is important to choose objects that are well-planned in time and help to illuminate the content of the excursion service topic.

The final part, like the introductory part, lasts 5-7 minutes and is not related to the excursion objects. Here are the final conclusions on the topic of the tour service, as well as information on other tour topics that can expand and deepen the topic covered today. The final part is as important as the introduction and the main part. While the tour service should be fun, it should not be loaded with unnecessary information flow, the method of presenting the information should not be boring, and it should be interestingly received by different categories of tourists. Therefore, the subject of the tour should be aimed at a specific category of tourists (adults, children, youth, urban or rural residents, various professions, foreign tourists, etc.). In an excursion service, such an approach is called a differential approach.

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